

LISTENING AND LEARNING OUR CLASSICAL MUSIC IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF FORMING NATIONAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: In the article, the attention paid to the art and culture of music in our country, the study and development of its rich heritage, the role of music pedagogy in the development of the field of music education and training, its role in education, Samples of Uzbek folk music, the content of manuals published by our scientists and composers, and important factors of forming a healthy worldview in youth education are given.

Keywords: Pedagogy, music pedagogy, upbringing, education, information, development, knowledge, skills, competence, pedagogical skills, didactics.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada yurtimizda musiqa san'ati va madaniyatiga berilayotgan e'tibor, uning boy me'rosini o'rganilishi va rivojlantirilishi, musiqa ta'limi va tarbiyasi sohasini rivojlanishida musiqa pedagogikasi fanining o'rni, ta'limda o'qitilishi, o'zbek xalq musiqa ijodi namunalari, olimlarimiz va bastakorlarimiz nashr etgan qo'lanmalar mazmuni, hamda yoshlar tarbiyasida sog'lom dunyoqarashni shakllantirishning muhim omillari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogika, musiqa pedagogikasi, tarbiya, ta'lim, ma'lumot, rivojlanish, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, pedagogik mahorat, didaktika.

Аннотация: В статье сделано внимание музыкальному искусству и культуре нашей страны, изучению и развитию ее богатого наследия, роли музыкальной педагогики в развитии сферы музыкального образования и обучения, ее роли в воспитании, приведены образцы узбекской народной музыки, содержание пособий, изданных нашими учеными и композиторами, а также важные факторы формирования здорового мировоззрения в воспитании молодежи.

Ключевые слова: Педагогика, музыкальная педагогика, воспитание, образование, информация, развитие, знания, умения, компетентность, педагогическое мастерство, дидактика.

The study and development of the rich heritage of musical art and culture is an important factor, and its teaching and development in education will help the free development of international achievements in the field of musical

education and performance. Such values are important in the development of the art of music.[1]

From time immemorial, music has been an integral part of human life, and it has gradually progressed from our ancestors to us. In particular, many treatises of great scholars such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abdurakhman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Najmiddin Kavkabi, Darvish Ali Changi information is provided. It is known that the peoples of Central Asia developed music and literature at very high levels in history. They are based on oral or historical constructions in creating their national music. In these musical repertoires, well-informed national literary genres have also taken their place. Among the types of national literature, the peoples of Central Asia used epics, songs, poems and collections of hadiths.

In our republic, great importance is attached to raising the cultural level of the population, finding and supporting young artists, and providing educational organizations with national musical instruments, music collections, and educational literature. "Increasing the musical knowledge and skills of pupils and students in educational institutions, forming love for national culture in their hearts, identifying and supporting young talents" is the priority of the development of culture and art. are directions. This requires clarifying the psychological-pedagogical and methodical features of developing the skills of listening and performing national music works in pupils, students, and improving the methodological conditions for developing the skills of listening to national music with the help of information technologies.[2]

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-637 dated September 23, 2020 "On Education", PD-60 of the Resident of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PD-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "Approving the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 on" decrees, dated May 3, 2019 No. PD-4307 "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work", 2021 PQ-5040 dated March 26 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs", PD-112 dated February 22, 2022 "To further develop the sphere of culture and art" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 31, 2019 No. 1059 "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" and in other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity, music serves to a certain extent the implementation of

the tasks defined in the priority directions of the development of the sphere of culture and art.[3]

In our new Uzbekistan, in recent years, including today, there have been updates and positive changes based on a new modern approach to the development of the education, culture and art system in all areas, and the factors of the effectiveness of the reforms in our country have been identified by well-known scientists, experts, researchers, also, with the participation of representatives of the private sector and prestigious international organizations, scientific practical conferences and seminars are being organized and held in order to create a scientific field. Its main purpose is to serve as a scientific and methodological resource for deepening the reforms implemented in our country, improving state programs, and defining new perspectives.

Paying special attention to the customs, traditions and rituals of our people in our country is of great importance nowadays, when the process of spiritual revival is accelerating. The Uzbek people have a rich, multi-layered and unique musical heritage. One of the main tasks of each of us is to thoroughly study and enjoy our history, national customs and traditions, and our spiritual and artistic heritage. In this regard, the just policy of our countryman and the construction of New Uzbekistan together with our country and people, material cultural heritage, restoration of our ancient values, examples of Uzbek folk music, status art, and the famous musicologist and scientist in our country and in the world. the opportunity to learn national classical tunes and songs related to the work of composers is expanding even more.[4]

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2022 No. PD-122 "On additional measures to further develop the sphere of culture and art", music and art in the field of education paid attention to. In this decision, the following decisions were made regarding music:

a) in general secondary educational institutions:

- in this decision, the skills of playing tunes on at least one of the national musical instruments listed in Appendix 1 will be taught, and a corresponding note will be made about this in their educational document (certificate);

- one study hour per week for music and, in addition to it, practical circles and faculty lessons on playing tunes on national musical instruments are held every week;

- it is mandatory for music teachers to have the ability to play tunes on at least one of the national instruments listed in Appendix 1 to this decision, and at least three from the 2023/2024 academic year;[4]

- within the educational hours allocated for the science of music, under the motto "Instrument accompanies my life", lessons on playing an instrument will be launched;

- provision of sheet music collections and special musical literature, provision of general education schools with textbooks and teaching-methodical manuals will be included in the system.

In our country, the promising projects implemented in all fields by the initiatives of the President Shavkat Mirziyoev, the large-scale creative works implemented in the areas are fundamentally changing not only the lifestyle of our people, but also the worldview. Such a noble process can be seen in the example of the high attention paid to the development of culture and art, to the people of creativity. In the last two or three years, about 20 decrees and decisions related to this field have been adopted. Efforts are being made to implement them. The decision of the President of November 28, 2021 "On approving the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is of particular importance as an important document aimed at eliminating existing problems and shortcomings in this field.

The process of learning melodies and songs by our people, the problem of revival of our centuries-old values has been studied for years. A number of scientific researches and studies are being carried out by experts and scientists in the field of music education and art in order to implement the decisions and decrees of our country's president, and methodical recommendations and educational methodical manuals are being published. The contents of these manuals include the art of Uzbek folk music, folk instruments and their history of origin and development, samples of sheet music collections of our national classical music, the lives and works of composers who contributed to the art of Uzbek national music. the way is covered. In this, an attempt is made to briefly refer to the tunes created by the people, the history of their creation, relatively complex genres, and the Uzbek musical culture and folk instruments that have been developing for many centuries.

There are several types of classes in educational institutions in order to create theoretical and practical skills in the perception of national melodies, the structure and performance of folk music genres in our youth: including traditional active and non-traditional interactive forms of education. is being conducted based on

A number of scientific researches on teaching the masterpieces of musical art to our youth and studying the services of our great scientists who made a

great contribution to its development and the material and cultural heritage left by them are bearing fruit. In particular, the collection of audio performance collections of Uzbek folk music published by academician Yunus Rajabi and the collections of sheet music published by our composers are being restored and improved and adapted by our creative scientists for playing in piano, dutor, gijjak, rubob. [6]

Also, some notable experiences of our famous artists and performers D.Zokirov, M.Mirzayev, R.Kasimov in this regard are reflected in the manuals published today. The works included in the collection of musical works in the manuals differ in terms of genre and type, and their distribution throughout the manual is based on the principle of "from simple to complex". In the content of the manual based on this method, it is focused on reflecting the musical traditions belonging to different oases of our country. The main goal of the reforms in the education system is to give students and young people a deep understanding of the Uzbek national songs based on the "step-by-step method" and the formation of skills to perform competently on folk instruments.

In order for our young people to listen to our national status songs, it is recommended to use the following systematic methods:

In the literature classes, the teacher should interpret and analyze the words of the national classical music of each status, explain ourselves in literary language and give them information about the content of the songs.

It is necessary to create artistic works suitable for national films and serials and connect them to our national status songs that match the events and events in their content. This experience is widely used mainly in Indian films.

It is necessary to multiply the versions of the singers who sing the singers who sing the samples of skillful performance by younger singers. Because it is appropriate if the voice timbre of the performer is within a certain age limit. Because most of our current famous stars are young singers. If the performer's voice is younger, it attracts people better. Most of our statuses were performed by our senior teachers. Voice timbre needs to be rejuvenated.[7]

It is necessary to collect the poems of about 250 makam songs, which were formed as makam in literature classes, and to recite the ghazals of these poets, which were performed as makam, and memorize them. It is necessary to connect the status songs learned by heart in the literature classes to the music culture lesson and sing the easy ones and listen to the complex ones.

Every nation has its own national traditions, values and holidays. In particular, the Uzbek people have a lot of national holiday wedding ceremonies. Our seasonal holidays are also very numerous and have ancient historical roots. It is necessary to include those that direct our feelings of gratitude and shkuhi to our statuses performed during our joyous holidays. On the contrary, we should listen more to the performance of our statuses that encourage patience and appreciation in our holidays and events dedicated to mourning and remembrance. We need to bring status into all aspects of our lives.

The performance of our statuses should be re-recorded by skilled singers and musicians on today's advanced instruments and in modern recording studios. It is necessary to involve experts in the field in the performance of maqams, analyze their chords as accurately as possible and harmonize chords on the basis of triads, then quadrats, to make maqam melodies attractive and pleasant to hear. In the performance of our current statuses, it is performed almost without chord harmony. It sounds like a dry tune to our listeners, who are used to hearing chords and harmonies. The methods should also be rounded off with instruments that give a method that is pleasing to the modern ear. Then the desire of the listeners to hear status tunes increases by certain percentages.[8]

For example, every month of the year has important dates. For example, every year on February 9, the Navoi event is held. Navoi's ghazals included in maqam songs should be read and interpreted at these events. It is these ghazals that should be heard performed by singers and musicians who are highly skilled in this field. This tradition should be widely used in events such as Baburkhanlik and Mashrabkhanlik.

Musical works taught to students in musical performance classes should be divided into 6 modules as a separate module, and each module should include 6 maqam melodic works, which are part of the instrumental difficulty section.

In singing lessons, students should be taught how to perform musical works, divided into 6 modules as a separate module.

A certain number of statuses are learned from each department, and the remaining statuses of similar size should be taught on the basis of independent educational forms. It is necessary to regularly monitor under the guidance of the teacher.

It is necessary to develop subjects suitable for teaching 6 statuses and divide them into semesters.

In subjects such as the history of music, Uzbek folk music, where theoretical groups are being taught, the theoretical concepts of status should be studied as 1 module as possible.

It is necessary to create such programs on such a foreign television and radio, where in each issue of the program, the history of the origin of our national status, the traditions of performance should be systematically covered. Then you need to filter these numbers and create a channel on social networks like YouTube Telegram and post them sequentially. Each status name search should result in status execution from the search.

In the process of listening to music in music culture classes, it is necessary to listen to the students' thoughts about what kind of emotional experiences they had when they listened to our national anthems. For example, students and students were asked what feelings they felt when listening to the song "Choli Irak".

Listening to the song, the students made the following good points:

- Patience.
- Giving thanks.
- Appreciation of parents
- Patriotism
- Family life
- Mercy and consequence
- Feeling our national traditions
- Thinking about the hereafter
- Restrain the lust
- Being a believer and a believer
- Not to eat someone's rights
- Not to betray
- Not to harm a person mentally and physically
- Feeling the musical history[9]

They said that they felt such feelings and that the above feelings were formed by enjoying the words and melodies of the statuses.

For the practical use of audio notes of tunes and songs created by our creative people and our talented singers and highly qualified composers over the years, it is appropriate to learn in parts from the early stages of the educational process. At the same time, it is extremely important to give pupils, students and young people not only technical capabilities, but also a deep understanding of national tunes and especially statuses.

In short, national classical music, which is considered one of the masterpieces created by our people, is expressed to a certain extent in every field, for example, in education, work and social relations. Murgak, from babies to enlightened old people, enjoys the benefits of art throughout his life, and on this basis, he fights mentally and physically for a brighter tomorrow.

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